

66. Agroforestry for carbon farming certification: how to demonstrate co-benefits for biodiversity and ecosystems?

EURAF Policy Briefing 66. 28.2.25, DOI [10.5281/zenodo.14937786](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14937786)

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EURAF is based in Montpellier, Brussels & Toledo (Transparency Register ID of [913270437706-82](https://www.transparencyregister.eu/lookup/913270437706-82)). It aims “to promote the adoption of agroforestry practices across Europe and support awareness, education, research, policy and investments which foster the use of trees on farms”. It has a network of 31 affiliated entities in 23 countries. Other EURAF Policy Briefings are listed [here](#). Contact: policy@euraf.net

Abstract

Policy Briefing 66 (v1) describes the clear benefits which agroforestry systems have for biodiversity and the protection of ecosystems. But how can these be demonstrated in carbon farming projects, without a monitoring complexity and timescale which makes the projects uneconomic? Biodiversity was the only one of the six “sustainability” elements recognised in the European Sustainable Finance Taxonomy which co-legislators of the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework insisted must show a clear co-benefit. For the other five areas (mitigation, adaptation, water resources, pollution and the circular economy) it is sufficient that projects should “do no significant harm”. Several potential indicators of biodiversity and ecosystem health are suggested for inclusion in the Carbon Farming Delegated Act of the CRCF, due to be published in summer 2025. We also propose a structure for an Agroforestry Carbon Farming Management Plan which sets out the activities and potential monitoring steps to be undertaken in agroforestry carbon farming projects.

1. Importance of biodiversity and ecosystems in the Carbon Removals Certification Framework

The final text of the Carbon Removals Certification Framework Regulation (CRCF, [2024/3012](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/3012)) indicates that carbon farming projects should, at least, do “no significant harm to the environment” in the six areas specified in the Sustainable Finance Taxonomy Regulation ([2020/852](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2020/852)). These areas are:

- A. climate change mitigation beyond the net carbon removal benefit and net soil emission reduction benefit referred to in the CRCF Regulation (i.e. enteric fermentation and slurry applications);
- B. climate change adaptation;
- C. the sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources;
- D. transition to a circular economy, including the efficient use of sustainably sourced bio-based materials;
- E. pollution prevention and control;
- F. **protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems**, including soil health as well as avoidance of land degradation.

Additionally, for the final of these (F) the carbon farming activity should “**at least generate co-benefits**”. It is stated (Recital 15) that “*co-benefits ... could increase the value of certified carbon removals or soil emission reductions*”.

Recital 24 states that “*Those minimum sustainability requirements should take into account the impact of the activity both **within and outside the Union** as well as local conditions, and, where appropriate, be consistent with the technical screening criteria for the ‘do no significant harm’ principle, and be in line with the sustainability and greenhouse gas emissions saving criteria for forest and agriculture biomass raw material laid down in Directive (EU) [2018/2001](#) (promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources)*”

The Sustainable Finance Taxonomy Regulation ([2020/852](#)) indicates that **technical screening criteria** for sustainability will be provided for “substantial contribution” and “no significant harm” in the areas of a) nature and biodiversity contribution, b) sustainable land use management, c) sustainable agricultural practices and d) sustainable forest management (Box 1). These screening criteria are introduced in Section 2.

BOX 1: “Substantial contribution” to the protection and restoration of biodiversity & ecosystems (Regulation 2020/852)

1. An economic activity shall qualify as contributing substantially to the protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems where that activity contributes substantially to protecting, conserving or restoring biodiversity or to achieving the good condition of ecosystems, or to protecting ecosystems that are already in good condition, through:
 - (a) **nature and biodiversity conservation**, including achieving favourable conservation status of natural and semi-natural habitats and species, or preventing their deterioration where they already have favourable conservation status, and protecting and restoring terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems in order to improve their condition and enhance their capacity to provide ecosystem services;
 - (b) **sustainable land use and management**, including adequate protection of soil biodiversity, land degradation neutrality and the remediation of contaminated sites;
 - (c) **sustainable agricultural practices**, including those that contribute to enhancing biodiversity or to halting or preventing the degradation of soils and other ecosystems, deforestation and habitat loss;
 - (d) **sustainable forest management**, including practices and uses of forests and forest land that contribute to enhancing biodiversity or to halting or preventing degradation of ecosystems, deforestation and habitat loss.
2. The Commission shall adopt a **Delegated Act** in accordance with Article 23 to:
 - (a) supplement paragraph 1 of this Article by establishing **technical screening criteria** for determining the conditions under which a specific economic activity qualifies as "contributing substantially" to the protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems; and
 - (b) supplement Article 17 (i.e. “Significant harm to environmental objectives”) by establishing, for each relevant environmental objective, **technical screening criteria** for determining whether an economic activity in respect of which technical screening criteria have been established pursuant to point (a) of this paragraph causes significant harm to one or more of those objectives.

Draft elements for an EU Certification methodology on carbon removals and soils emission reductions under the CRCF Regulation for the activity “Soil Carbon in Mineral Soils and Agroforestry” were provided by DG CLIMA

in October 2024 (DG-CLIMA, 2024). EURAF commented on these ([14.11.24](#)) and is updating EURAF [Policy Briefing #20](#) on MRV for agroforestry carbon farming accordingly.

2. Technical Screening Criteria options for a “co-benefit” related to the protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems

Technical Screening Criteria (Appendix B) for a “**substantial-contribution**” to the protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems were published in June 2023 as [Annex 4](#) to Regulation 2020/852, following discussion in the “[Platform on Sustainable Finance](#)”, and recommendations from a [Technical Working Group](#).¹ They are extremely demanding: involving detailed descriptions of the species and habitats concerned, connectivity between habitats and detailed management plans and procedures for regular audit and guarantees of permanence. They **cannot be regarded as practical for a carbon farming project**, nor do they relate to the wording in the CRCF which merely calls for a “**co-benefit**” rather than a “**substantial contribution**”.

As an alternative to these complicated criteria, DG CLIMA proposed using two of the tree indicators of agricultural biodiversity included in the Nature Restoration Regulation to demonstrate a "co-benefit" (see [EURAF Policy Briefing #18](#)), viz: a) **stock of organic carbon** in cropland mineral soils, b) **share of agricultural land with high-diversity landscape features**. However this pragmatic approach is unlikely to be sufficient to demonstrate the "co-benefit" expected by the co-legislators, and by many contributors to the DG CLIMA consultation (DG-CLIMA, 2024) on carbon farming monitoring, reporting and verification.²

In December 2023 EURAF suggested ([Policy Briefing #28](#)) a mandatory Agroforestry Carbon Farming (ACF) Management Plan to help in the evaluation of sustainability impacts. This could also be linked to “chain of custody” certification schemes for Trees outside Forests developed by the Programme for Endorsement of Forest Certification, or similar approaches linked to the Forest Stewardship Council. The draft ACF Management Plan suggested in Section 4 is modelled on the Forest Management Plan included in the Sustainable Finance Taxonomy for forestry projects.

3. Impacts of Agroforestry on biodiversity and protection of ecosystems

Agroforestry systems generally increase **biodiversity** by creating diverse habitats with woody and herbaceous plant species which support a wider range of wildlife than monocultures (Torralba *et al.*, 2016; Plexida *et al.*, 2018; Prevedello, Almeida-Gomes and Lindenmayer, 2018; Mupepele, Keller and Dormann, 2020; Boinot *et al.*, 2022; Triquet *et al.*, 2024). This structural complexity is particularly beneficial when native trees are used, since they are better adapted to local conditions (Santos *et al.*, 2022), but climate change in Europe is often so rapid that non-native tree species or provenances from a more southerly range are better adapted (Dimitrova *et al.*, 2022). A higher abundance of beneficial insects can be supported by agroforestry, including pollinators and natural predators of pests, and this contributes to better pest control and pollination services (Bentrup *et al.*, 2019; Staton *et al.*, 2019; Pantera *et al.*, 2021).

Tree rows in arable lands create a zone of refuge, which is less disturbed by agricultural machinery and this permits a wide range of species to survive and thrive, including plants, mosses, insects, mammals, amphibians, reptiles, earthworms, and spiders. Tree rows have varying roles, depending on the species. They can provide more food and wintering areas for pollinators feeding (Kay *et al.*, 2020), habitats for birds, spiders and ground beetles (Bailey *et al.*, 2010), greater seasonal variation in nectar for pollinators (Bertrand *et al.*, 2019), and more diverse habitats (Andersen, 2017) for birds (Edo, Entling and Rösch, 2024) and bats (Edo *et al.*, 2025). Tree rows constitute protected corridors inside the plots, and allow animals to move without passing through the cultivated zones. Thanks to this structure, agroforestry plots are easy to traverse by mobile species, and provide green networks across the landscape, for example by joining isolated woodlands (Burel *et al.*, 2013).

¹ see comments from [WWF](#) on the Working Group's recommendations

² See comments from EURAF [here](#)

Trees interspersed in crops or pasture bring diversified habitats, and permit species threatened by agricultural intensification to survive. Greater use of agroforestry is specifically recommended by the International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN) as a mechanism to protect threatened bee species in Europe (Nieto *et al.*, 2014). The diversity of species is generally higher in semi-open areas than in areas which are completely wooded or completely herbaceous. At the landscape scale, agroforestry plots change the conditions for breeding and feeding of mobile species, from birds to large mammals, from bats to frogs, and including vertebrates in general. Most changes are beneficial (Schmidt *et al.*, 2022) but species which require large areas of open heathland, like skylarks, may suffer (Hagist, 2021; Zitzmann and Langhof, 2023).

In agricultural areas, some habitats are particularly rare, like hollow, dead or decomposing trees, or dead trunks and branches lying on the ground, which form rich habitats for detritus feeders. These habitats conceal many rare and endangered species. In responsible agroforestry management some older trees should be retained, as their defects in shape (e.g. tree cavities, broken trunks and branches) can provide a habitat for many tree-dwelling species.

Another example of agroforestry benefits on biodiversity is given by bats. Bats are rarely found in cultivated areas. Pesticide treatments reduce their food supply, and they need to optimise their expenditure of foraging energy. Radar tracking shows that agroforestry alleys can be real highways for bats (Disca, 2003), since they follow the tree lines and hunt intensely. It remains to be seen what insects are on their menu: whether it is the trees or the accompanying herbaceous vegetation that contributes most to the insects consumed (Wolfrum, 2014; Edo *et al.*, 2025).

In terms of **ecosystem protection**, agroforestry clearly improves soil health by increasing organic matter, enhancing nutrient cycling, and reducing erosion (Kay *et al.*, 2019; Castle *et al.*, 2022). The presence of trees helps stabilize soil and prevents nutrient leaching, contributing to long-term soil fertility (Schoeneberger *et al.*, 2012; Kay *et al.*, 2019). Agroforestry systems also enhance water management by improving infiltration rates, reducing runoff, maintaining soil moisture and diverting flood water (Sollen-Norrlin, Ghaley and Rintoul, 2020; Zhu *et al.*, 2020). This is particularly important in areas prone to drought or flooding. In addition to biodiversity and ecosystem protection, agroforestry contributes significantly to the other five EU measures of sustainability: climate-mitigation, climate-adaptation, water resources, control of pollution and the circular economy (Torralba *et al.*, 2016; García de Jalón *et al.*, 2018; Rois-Díaz *et al.*, 2018).

Despite their wide variation, agroforestry systems have in common that they provide at least two different types of marketable products (food, feed or timber), and environmental benefits (Pimentel and Wightman, 1999; Jose, 2009). In Europe, many traditional agroforestry systems have been classified as high-nature-value and high-biodiversity systems (McNeely and Schroth, 2006; Price, 2013; Moreno *et al.*, 2018) and are therefore listed in the EU Habitats Directive and protected within the NATURA 2000 network, as for instance the Dehesa and Montado areas in Portugal.

Agroforestry carbon farming fits well with the Commission's recently published "Strategic Dialogue on the Future of Agriculture" (European Commission, 2024), which mentions carbon more than 20 times and agroforestry five times. It also conforms with recent attempts to develop methodologies for "biodiversity credits" (Nature Finance, 2023; Wunder *et al.*, 2024; Yunyue *et al.*, 2024), or "nature credits" (Swinfield *et al.*, 2024; European Commission, 2025). The EU Commission Vision for Agriculture and Food (European Commission, 2025) mentions nature credits as "*units of nature-positive actions, representing quantified and certified high-quality nature-positive outcomes. A number of existing schemes developed by commercial operators and ongoing pilot projects, both at EU and international level, show the important potential for such projects, on which further work can be built.*"

4. Agroforestry Carbon Farming (ACF) Management Plan

EURAF suggests that Agroforestry Carbon Farming (ACF) operations greater than 1 ha are covered by an ACF Management Plan. This should have a duration of at least ten years, or the rotation period planned for the agroforestry area. The Plan would normally be developed prior to the start of the activity (perhaps with the

assistance of a CAP Ecoscheme) and will be continuously updated. Agroforestry plantations less than 6 years old can be included in a post-hoc Management Plan if initial growth of the plantation has been satisfactory. The Plan will show all areas of ACF included in the carbon farming activity, and neighbouring parcels of forest or agricultural land.

An agroforestry parcel will be defined as **agricultural land** with an actual or planned tree crown cover above a minimum-threshold set by the Member State³, including boundary trees. The upper threshold of "agroforestry" is already set by Member States in their national forest definitions, as described in Annex II of the EU LULUCF Regulation (2018/841) and used in their annual GHG Inventories to the UNFCCC. (EURAF [Policy Briefing #15](#)).

The ACF Management Plan should include all elements required by the national law relating to environmental impact and monitoring, with additional elements needed for GHG monitoring reporting and verification (MRV) (BOX 2)

BOX 2: Suggested elements for an Agroforestry Carbon Farming Management Plan

- A. Location of the parcels and boundaries using codes from the national IACS/LPIS system (or equivalent)
- B. Location of neighbouring forest and agricultural blocks, showing habitat linkages between wooded areas and the role of ACF parcels in fire-management plans for adjacent forests.
- C. Baseline estimates of carbon-stocks in each certified parcel including soils and above-ground biomass
- D. Management goals, design, species and predicted carbon sequestration of areas covered by trees
- E. Management goals and predicted carbon sequestration of the intercropped or grazed alleys;
- F. Strategies and activities planned to reach the management goals (e.g. maximising biodiversity if this is required), including a time-line over the rotation;
- G. Environmental context of the farm(s), including main existing and intended tree species
- H. Details of access, environmental constraints, registered landscape-features and legal restrictions on land-use change;
- I. Details of engagement with neighbours and local stakeholders, in accordance best practice nationally;
- J. Assessment of agroforestry related risks, including fires, pests and diseases outbreaks and plans to mitigate these
- K. Assessment of impact on food production of the farm(s) included in the plan;
- L. Summary "do no significant harm" (DNSH) criteria for other "non-biodiversity" areas of "sustainability"

ACF activities will follow the best tree, crop, and livestock practices recommended by national forestry or agricultural advisory services, or by the national affiliates of the European Agroforestry Federation (www.agroforestry.net). CAP tree-planting and management grants should be used, where possible, to establish the ACF area, and the CAP Conditionality rules and rules for Ecoschemes, Investment Measures and/or Agri-Environment-Climate Measures should be adhered to. Areas which are accepted using the ACF rules of an approved Certification Body should comply with the Implementing and Delegated Acts of the Carbon Removals Certification Framework (DG CLIMA, 2023). Where possible, activities should also follow the "Pan-European Guidelines for Afforestation and Reforestation with a special focus on the provisions of the UNFCCC"⁴

Agroforestry **can** also be established on drained peatlands, where trees will provide both productive and protective functions, but in such areas the ACF Management Plan should be mandatory irrespective of the planting-block size, and best available practices for peatland conservation should be followed (Widayati, Tata and van Noordwijk, 2016; Bārdulis *et al.*, 2022).

³ EURAF advises Member States to select either the threshold of 5% used by the FAO for "Other Wooded Land" or 10% - used by the FAO for Forest.

⁴ These are [rather old but still important](#) regarding forest definitions and the UNFCCC Marrakesh Accords

Marketing of timber from ACF should comply with the due diligence obligation and legality requirements laid down in Regulation (EU) No [995/2010](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council⁵. Compliance with PEFC “[Trees Outside Forests](#)” procedures (or the FSC equivalent when developed) is also recommended.

5. Biodiversity and Ecosystem Indicators which could be monitored periodically in agroforestry carbon farming

Despite the positive effects on biodiversity and ecosystems, discussed above, there is a lack of standard indicators to be used at farm and parcel scale. The DigitAF project aims to create a tool capable of assessing biodiversity effects in different types of agroforestry systems, but won't apply in-situ monitoring due to a lack of standard indicators and the time needed to observe results (Vandendriessche *et al.*, 2023). Thus, it will focus on evidence-based literature findings. In addition, the DigitAF project has recommended a number of existing CAP Impact Indicators (EURAF [Policy Briefing #69](#)) which could be used at farm or parcel scale for the valuation of environmental benefits of agroforestry and other Nature Based Solutions.

- **I.10 Greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture**: this national indicator can be derived at farm and partial scale, and provides a link to national GHG emission calculation - except that few MS currently include wall-to-wall mapping of agricultural or forestry parcels, and many ignore the impact of trees outside forests.
- **I.11 Soil organic carbon in agricultural land** : this indicator is currently based on the LUCAS soil survey and is not available at farm or parcel scale. The intention in the [Farm Sustainability Tool](#) was that Member States would make available soil analysis data at parcel scale - but none have so far done this.
- **I.12 Sustainable production of renewable energy from agriculture and forestry** - this is currently published at a national scale, but it could be extended to the farm scale by increased use of Life-Cycle analysis of farms (Goglio *et al.*, 2015)
- **I.13 Soil erosion by water** - again this is usually published at regional scale (NUTS2) but the RUSLE equation could be applied to all EU farms and parcels and made available through the LPIS.
- **I.14 Ammonia emissions from agriculture** - MS publish data based on manure management and fertilisation data. Once the EU Farm Sustainability Tool is provided by MS, it could be calculated at a farm scale.
- **I.15 Gross nutrient balance (N, P) on agricultural land (kg N & P/ha/yr)**: again this is reported only at a national scale, when the data potentially exists in the LPIS and the FaST tool for it to be calculated for farms and parcels.
- **I.16 Nitrates in groundwater** (percent of water stations with nitrate concentration over 50 mg/l per Directive 91/676/EEC). Member States differ in the frequency of sampling and the density of the monitored stations, but the option exists to publish this data at a river basin level.
- **I.17 Water Exploitation Index +** (percent of water use over the renewable water resources available): again this is usually published at a national level but would be very useful at a basin or sub-basin level.
- **I.19 Increasing farmland bird populations**⁶. This, again, is usually published at a national level. The species measured differ between countries, although a weighted "EU basket of species" is available. Most species will benefit from agroforestry hedgerows and trees, but some species (e.g. skylark and lapwing) prefer open land - therefore a less integrated index is needed.
- **I.20b Percent of species and habitats of community interest related to agriculture with stable or increasing trends**: this is published at NUTS 2/3 level and relates to very broad habitat types
- **I.20a Percentage of pollinator species of community interest related to agriculture with stable or increasing trends**: this is again only available at NUTS 2/3 level
- **I.21 Agricultural land covered with landscape features**⁷: this is again currently only available at NUTS 3 (province) level based on LUCAS data from the [JRC](#), or for woody landscape features based on Copernicus from the [EEA](#). Member States have been asked in the NRR to develop their own, more detailed, monitoring methodologies by August 2025, as one of the three indicators of Agricultural Diversity.

⁵ Regulation (EU) No 995/2010 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 October 2010 laying down the obligations of operators who place timber and timber products on the market (OJ L 295, 12.11.2010, p. 23).

⁶ A multi-species composite index, which integrates the abundance and the diversity of a selection of common bird species associated with specific habitats. Rare species are excluded. Three groups of bird species are represented: common farmland species (39 species), common forest species (34 species) and all common bird species (168 species; including farmland and forest species). The indices are presented for EU-aggregates only and with smoothed values. The European Bird Census Council and its Pan-European Common Bird Monitoring Scheme programme delivers data from 26 Member States. MT is not covered ([link](#))

⁷ Agricultural landscape features are small fragments of non-productive (sic) natural or semi-natural vegetation in agricultural landscapes which provide ecosystem services and support for biodiversity. This definition includes several non-productive elements of European agricultural landscapes, such as hedges, ponds, ditches, trees in line or in group or isolated, field margins, terraces, dry-stone or earth walls, planted areas, individual monumental trees, springs or historic canal networks. ([link](#))

Two additional indices are not CAP Impact Indicators (European Commission, 2023), but were suggested for monitoring biodiversity and ecosystem health in the Nature Restoration Regulation (EURAF [Policy Briefing #18](#)) are:

- **Pollinator diversity and populations** (NRR Art. 10) - with a NRR Delegated Act proposed on methodologies by [August 2025](#).
- **Grassland Butterfly Index** (NRR Art 11) - which measures changes in population abundance at EU level of 15 grassland butterfly species, using 1991 as reference year, with values calculated every year by the European Butterfly Monitoring Scheme partnership, distributed by the European Environmental Agency, and further provided by Eurostat. ([link](#))

The Ecologic Institute, in collaboration with a CREDIBLE Project Focus Group have developed a [Policy Briefing](#) on achieving sustainability through carbon farming certification. In the area of biodiversity and ecosystems they suggest the following following possibilities:

- **number of indicator species for habitat quality**
- **% area of natural, productive and restored habitats;**
- **% edge-of-field in native species;**
- **area of restored/ created habitats ha**

Other, more modern, techniques which need further evaluation include:

- **Soil Biological Quality Index** (QBS-ar) - which is based on the concept that the number of microarthropod groups morphologically well adapted to the soil is higher in high quality soils than in low quality soils (Menta *et al.*, 2018; Maienza *et al.*, 2022)
- **E-DNA Analysis** – which uses metabarcoding or metagenomic DNA technology to evaluate soil biodiversity (Hossain *et al.*, 2025) - and is offered by an increasing number of European companies (e.g. [Ramboll](#), [SGS AllGenetics](#)).

6. Biodiversity at the 7th European Agroforestry Conference, Brno May 2024

The Seventh [European Agroforestry Conference](#) held in Brno, Czech Republic gathered farmers, foresters, researchers and policy makers to consider the state of agroforestry in Europe and temperate regions more broadly. Participants agreed a [declaration](#) which highlighted the contribution agroforestry makes to the 6 areas of environmental sustainability in the EU Taxonomy - climate-mitigation, climate-adaptation, pollution, water-resources, circular economy and biodiversity-ecosystems. Session 1.3 covered biodiversity and included the following presentations:

- Monitoring of biodiversity effects of agroforestry: start of a long-term experiment in Hesse, Germany ([Altman et al, 2024](#))
- Agroforestry systems are significantly increasing biodiversity of ground beetles (Carabidae) ([Weger & Bubenik, 2024](#))
- Agroforestry systems to support bat conservation in Europe ([Edo et al, 2024](#))
- Acoustic bird monitoring in 20 Swiss agroforestry systems: Challenges and opportunities ([Kunzelmann et al 2024](#))
- Plant community response to solitary trees in traditional wood pastures of Southern Transylvania, Romania ([Hang Le, 2024](#))
- Vegetation Diversity and Weed-pressure in Alley-cropping Agroforestry in Switzerland. ([Roberti, 2024](#))
- Arthropod Community Extraction from Soil Samples using a MACFADYEN Extractor in a Silvopasture ([Hirchvogel et al, 2024](#))
- Effect of intercropping of Paulownia and buckwheat on soil microbial biodiversity and enzymatic activity ([Jama-Rodenska et al, 2024](#))
- Exploring food forest soil biodiversity: from microbes to earthworms ([Van Zanden et al. 2024](#)).
- Effects of land use change on soil microbial functioning in a long-term agroforestry system ([Olave et al, 2024](#)).
- What can biodiversity do for agroforestry? ([Smith, 2024](#))
- Effect of cropping system on soil mesofauna diversity and abundance: An olive alley agroforestry ([Tadesse et al, 2024](#))
- Service tree, suitable tree for agroforestry systems ([Hrdoušek 2024](#))

- The beekeeping value of buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum*) in intercropping with oxytree (*Paulownia elongata* x *P. fortunei*) ([Marek Liszewski, 2024](#))
- The impact of buffer tree strips on diversity of different groups of Arthropods in organic arable land ([Radzikowski, 2024](#))
- Tree diversity in German alley cropping research and practice ([Weckenbrock, 2024](#))

7. Conclusion

This is one of four Policy Briefings dealing with the areas of sustainability contained in the Environment Delegated Act of the Sustainable Finance Taxonomy. The Regulation on Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming stipulates that carbon farming schemes should generate a positive co-benefit in the area of biodiversity and ecosystem protection. We suggest that an agroforestry carbon farming management plan will address much of this requirement, and a structure was suggested in December 2023, as an extension of the Sustainable Finance Taxonomy (EURAF [Policy Briefing #28](#)). The Taxonomy already contains management plan structures for Forestry and Paludiculture projects, and it is regretted that DG FISMA has not acted on the recommendations made by EURAF. In addition to the management plan options exist for farm and plot scale monitoring of some of the already collected CAP statistics, and modern techniques such as E-DNA. A tool is being developed by the [DigitAF Project](#) which predicts the consequences on biodiversity of different agroforestry designs and species mixtures based on artificial intelligence methods and a comprehensive database of research literature.

8. Annex A: Technical Screening Criteria for a “Substantial Contribution” to protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems”

Abridged from the Sustainable Finance Taxonomy - Environment Delegated Act Annex 4 ([C2023 3851](#))

1. General conditions The activity contributes to at least one of the following: (a) maintaining good condition of ecosystems, species, habitats or of habitats of species; (b) re-establishing or restoring ecosystems, habitats or habitats of species towards or to good condition, including through increasing their area or range.

2. Initial description of the area covered by the conservation activity. The activity takes place in an area with a detailed description of its initial ecological conditions which contains the following elements: a) mapping of the current habitats and their condition; b) where applicable, the protection status of the area; c) characterisation of the situation of the main species in terms of conservation relevance present in the area (including list of species, approximate size of the population, approximate size of the habitat of the species and its quality, period during which the area is used by the species); d) the importance of the area to reaching good condition of species, habitats or habitats of species at regional, national or international level as appropriate; e) where relevant, the potential for improving the condition of species, habitats or habitats of species present on the area or re-establishing habitats or habitats of species in the area or to enhance connectivity between habitats

3. Management plan or equivalent instrument. The area is covered by a management plan or by an equivalent instrument, such as a restoration plan, which is regularly updated and in any case at least every ten years, and contains the following information: a description of the expected contribution of the area to the nature conservation objectives set by the competent nature or environment authority considering the regional, national, Union and international legal and policy context; b) the list of species, habitats and habitats of the species that will benefit from the conservation measures (hereafter “targeted habitats and species”); c) the duration of the plan and a clear description of the conservation objectives for each targeted habitat and species and of the corresponding conservation measures that address identified pressures and threats, including the expected deadline for the achievement of the conservation objectives. In case the deadlines exceed the duration of the management plan, the expected progress (milestones) towards achievement is defined; d) a description of the threats and pressures that could hinder the achievement of the conservation objectives, including projected habitat transformations caused by climate change; e) the measures to ensure that all DNSH criteria for this activity are achieved; f) consideration of societal issues (including preservation of landscape, consultation of stakeholders in accordance with the terms and conditions laid down in national law); g) where applicable, a description of enhanced ecosystem services, such as carbon storage, water purification, flood protection, erosion prevention, pollination, recreational opportunities, and wider socio-economic benefits; h) a monitoring scheme with specific and relevant indicators, allowing to measure progress towards achieving the conservation objectives and an identification of corrective measures as necessary; i) the persons and organisations involved in the management or restoration of the area and, if relevant, the necessary

collaborations or partnerships to put in place to achieve the conservation objectives; j) the measures taken to ensure transparency about the conservation objectives, the conservation measures and the monitoring and its results; k) the funding necessary for implementing the conservation measures, for the monitoring of the area and its audit.

4. Audit. The initial description of the conservation area and the management plan or equivalent instrument specified in points 2 and 3 are verified by an independent third-party certifier at the start of the conservation activity. At the end of the duration of the management plan or equivalent instrument and at least every ten years, the achievement of the objectives set at the start of the management plan and the respect of the DNSH criteria are verified. The verification includes an updated detailed description of the ecological conditions of the area as specified in point 2, an evaluation of the effectiveness of the conservation measures, and of the achievement of the conservation objectives, an evaluation of an updated version of the management plan or equivalent instrument, and the recommendations for the next management plan or equivalent instrument. Verification will be carried out by either of the following: (a) the relevant national competent authorities; (b) an independent third-party certifier, at the request of national authorities or the operator of the activity. In order to reduce costs, audits may be performed together with any forest certification, land-use certification, biodiversity certification, climate certification or other audit. The independent third-party certifier may not have any conflict of interest with the owner or the funder and may not be involved in the development or operation of the activity. As a result of the verification, the certifier issues an audit report.

5. Guarantee of permanence In accordance with national law, the area on which the activity takes place is covered by one of the following measures: the area is classified as a protected area in line with the IUCN Protected Area Categories System, as a Natura 2000 site under Directive 92/43/EEC, or as an Other Effective area-based Conservation Measure (OECM), by national law or under an international convention to which the country is signatory and is effectively managed to prevent deterioration and enable the recovery of species and habitats or habitats of species; the area is destined to restoration or conservation in a statutory land, freshwater or maritime use plan approved by the competent authorities; the area is the subject to a public or private contractual arrangement that can ensure that the conservation objectives can be achieved and maintained.

9. References

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This Policy Briefing is an output from the [Carbon Farming Med Project](#). CF-MED runs from January 2024 to September 2026 and is a consortium of 9 European and international partners. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union.